

African Coordinating Mechanism

What is it?

A formal regional structure for supporting biodiversity information management on the continent

Strategic Objectives

Six strategic priority areas to advance the African biodiversity informatics efforts

1

Strengthen capacity to mobilise foundational data & fill knowledge gaps

2

Deliver data across the data-science-policy interface

3

Build institutional capacity in data management

4

Leverage science, technology and innovation to achieve the SDG's

5

Strengthen regional engagement

6

Build a strong African platform for biodiversity informatics partnerships

Key Achievements

Science Review and Research Priorities

Science Review of literature citing GBIF - Biodiversity in Africa

Invasive alien species: Building national watch lists for invasive alien species

Public health: Mapping the niche of Ebola host animals

Food security: Conserving genetic diversity of crops in West Africa

Thematic Use of GBIF Mediated Data for African Biodiversity*

- Advancing biodiversity science
- Biodiversity and human health
- Data management
- Food, farming and biofuels
- Impact of climate change
- Invasive alien species

* Summary 2011-2017, GBIF science review

Key Achievements

- 10** Voting country participants
- 11** Associate country participants
- 4** Participant organisations

The achievements of the GBIF-Africa Partnership

Data

More than

30 MILLION

Primary biodiversity data records mobilised by regional members

Funding

The GBIF-Africa Nodes have leveraged more than

US\$ 9 MILLION
in funding since 2014

Capacity Building

Continuous regional engagements since

2010

Approximate 50 BID & 11 CESP projects enabling training and capacity development

Action Plan

The ACM will enable the implementation of the **holistic action plan** that will foster a dynamic, capacitated network in biodiversity informatics able to generate, publish and use biodiversity data for sustainable development.

Regional Presence

The need for regional coordinating offices has been placed on the GBIF agenda for the first time, since adopting a regional approach, at the 2019 GBIF Governing Board. This was highlighted in the 20 year review

Secure Funding

Through the ACM explore funding avenues with governments and other funding agencies that has a strong focus on promoting science, technology and innovation.

Catalytic Projects

The conceptualisation and development of catalytic projects, like mass digitization, to enable activities to support the implementation of the ACM

Community of Practice

The ACM will explore a broader community of practice for biodiversity informatics initiatives. The aim is to enhance the use of data in of support science, technology, innovation and conservation outcomes.

Call to Action

Funders, National Institutions, Science Councils, Governments, Academia,

**Become part of
our Africa
biodiversity
informatics
network**

**Invest in the
Africa
Biodiversity
informatics
community**

Share your data

**Share your
knowledge and
expertise to build
capacity**

**Use the available
technology, platforms
and tools**

Support the data revolution by ensuring that data supports open science and decision making at the national, regional and global policy levels.

Partnerships

More Information

The African Coordinating Mechanism Report

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Resources

**Africa Coordinating
Mechanism
presentation**

Benin GBIF Node

**SANBI-GBIF Fitness
for Use Training**

**SANBI
Biodiversity Advisor**

**Node Managers
training**

**Masters program in
Biodiversity
Informatics**

**Data Use for
Decision Making**

**Biodiversity
Informatics Training**

GBIF

**JRS grants led by
African Nodes**

GBIF e-Learning